

TABLE 2. DETERMINATION OF SODIUM CINNAMATE
Time—3 min.

Sl. No.	Mercuric chloride of 0.01M added = 25 ml.			Sodium cinnamate		% Error
	Iodine solution taken 0.0023N ml	Hypo. of 0.01N ml	Iodine consumed as 0.01N ml	Taken mg.	Found mg.	
1.	100.0	23.40*	--	--	--	
2.	-do-	17.00	6.40	5.44	5.46	+0.36
3.	-do-	13.78	9.62	8.16	8.16	Nil
4.	-do-	10.53	12.87	10.88	10.92	+0.36
5.	-do-	7.38	16.02	13.60	13.61	+0.07

* Blank reading in terms of 0.01N Hypo.

Effect of Iodide Ions : The effect of iodide ion concentration on reaction was studied. It is observed that the reaction is incomplete in 3 minutes time in the presence of iodide ions and hence low results are afforded for cinnamic acid.

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Spectrophotometric Studies of the Chelates of Iron(III) : 2-Hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone thiosemicarbazone System

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SALICYLALDEHYDE and 2-hydroxyphenones offer an interesting field of study as reagents for spectrophotometric studies of iron(III)¹⁻⁸. The chelating tendencies of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone have been studied by various workers⁹⁻¹¹, however, the analytical potentialities of 2-hydroxyphenone thiosemicarbazones have not been investigated fully. The present paper reports the results of spectrophotometric studies of the green coloured solution formed when iron(III) salts react with alcoholic solution of the 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (5MeOATS).

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-5-Methyl acetophenone (5MeOHA) was prepared as described earlier¹². The 5MeOATS was obtained as yellow crystals by refluxing the 1:1 note of 5MeOHA and thiosemicarbazide in methanol for 1½ hr. The product was purified by recrystallization from acetic acid. The standard solutions, temperature, medium, absorbance and pH measurements were made as described earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

The nature of the complexes was determined by the method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹³. Only one complex with $\lambda_{max} = 645$ nm is formed under the conditions employed (pH $\approx$ 2.0). The 1:1 composition of the complex was determined by Job's method¹⁴ using equimolar and non equimolar metal and reagent solutions, the Slope ratio method¹⁵, and mole-ratio method. It was found that concentration of HNO₃ had a marked effect on the colour intensity of the complex.

The apparent stability constant of the complex log K = 4.0 ± 0.1 was calculated by the method of Mukherji and Dey¹⁷.

Beer's law : A series of solutions, each with a pH = 2.2 and containing the same concentration (5 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the reagent but varying (from 5 × 10⁻⁶ M to 2 × 10⁻⁴ M) concentration of iron(III) were prepared and their absorbances were measured at 645 nm. The results show that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.5 to 8 µg iron(III) per ml.

Effect of diverse ions : The interference due to diverse metal ions on the colour intensity of the complex was studied and the results are summarized in the following table.

TABLE		
Foreign ion	Added as	Tolerance limit µg/100 ml
VO ⁺⁺	VOSO ₄ ·H ₂ O	None
Cu ⁺⁺	CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	None
Zn ⁺⁺	Zn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	1000
Co ⁺⁺	Co(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	850
Mn ⁺⁺	Mn(ClO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	800
Ni ⁺⁺	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	850

Determination of the composition of complexes of iron(III) with oxalate and EDTA by equilibrium with coloured Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² complex in isomolar series :

The method is similar to the one described earlier¹⁸⁻²⁰. The coloured solution of Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) was prepared by mixing equal volumes of iron(III) (2 × 10⁻⁴ M) and 5MeOHATS (1 × 10⁻³ M) solutions. (acidity w.r.t. HNO₃ is $\sim$ 1 × 10⁻² M). A series of mixtures was then prepared using Fe(5MeOATS)⁺² (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) and Na₂EDTA/ammonium

oxalate ($1 \times 10^{-4} M$ in $0.01 M$ HNO_3) in which the proportion of the two was continuously varied, the absorbances were measured at 645 nm

The maximum change in absorbance is observed when $Fe(5MeOATS)^{+2}$ and EDTA or oxalate are present in equimolar proportion. It may be concluded, therefore, that iron(III) forms 1:1 complexes with $EDTA^{-4}$ and $C_2O_4^{-2}$.

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Chemical Investigation of the Barks of *Tecomella undulata*, *Heterophragma adenophyllum* and *Millingtonia hortensis* (Bignoniaceae)

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WE have recently reported the isolation and identification of lapachol, dehydrotectol, veratric acid and β -sitosterol from the bark of *T. undulata* and

β -sitosterol, lapachol and β -sitosterol from the heart-woods of *H. adenophyllum* and *M. hortensis* respectively¹. No work has been done on the barks of *H. adenophyllum* and *M. hortensis*. In this communication we report the isolation of *n*-hentriacontanol and ϵ -sitosterol from the bark of *T. undulata* and *n*-hentriacontanol and β -sitosterol from the barks of *H. adenophyllum* and *M. hortensis*.

The ether-soluble fraction of the benzene extract of bark of *T. undulata* was further fractionated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over Brockmannalumina (deactivated with 10% acetic acid). The fraction from petrol:benzene (1:1) gave a colourless compound, m.p. 83°–84° and fraction from benzene (100%) gave colourless needles, m.p. 143°–144°

The coarsely powdered bark of *Heterophragma adenophyllum* (2 kg) was extracted with boiling benzene for 3×12 hr. Complete removal of the solvent at reduced pressure gave an orange-yellow waxy material (3.00 g.). It was chromatographed over deactivated alumina (125 g) yielding a colourless compound (0.05 g), m.p. 81°–82° from petrol:benzene (1:1) fraction and another colourless compound (1.50 g), m.p. 134°–135° from petrol:benzene (1:4) fraction

Similarly, coarsely powdered bark of *Millingtonia hortensis* (2 kg) was extracted with benzene for 3×12 hr. Removal of the solvent at reduced pressure gave a reddish brown mass (3 g). It was chromatographed over deactivated alumina (125 g) and gave a colourless compound (0.05 g), m.p. 82°–83°, from petrol:benzene (1:1) fraction and another colourless compound (1.25 g), m.p. 134°–135°, from the benzene (100%) fraction

All the three compounds, m.p. 81°–84°, isolated from different barks, were recrystallised from acetone:ether (5:1) as colourless granules; m.p. 84°–85°. These were all homogeneous on T.L.C., using silicagel G adsorbent, C_6H_6 -EtOAc solvent and 1% acidic ceric sulphate developer

The I.R. spectrum showed adsorption at 3300 ($-OH$ stretching due to polymeric association), 2900, 2818 ($C-H$ stretching), 1472 ($-CH_2$ bending), 1379 ($C-CH_3$ bending), 1060 ($C-O$ stretching of a primary alcohol) and doublet at 730 and 720 [$-(CH_2)_n$ -bending ($n > 4$) vibration due to straight chain methylene groups]

The mass spectrum of all showed molecular ion peak at m/e 452. Besides the peak at m/e 31 due to $CH_2 = OH$, significant peaks, at low masses, found were m/e 45, 59, 73, etc. resulting from cleavage at $C-C$ bonds successively removed from oxygen atom. The ions at high mass end of spectrum occurred at the intervals of fourteen as expected² for a higher primary alcohol. A $M-18$ peak at m/e 434 caused by the loss of water and common to mass spectrum of alcohols could be detected³. A close study of